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JUDICIAL INDEPENDENCE IN NIGERIA: BETWEEN GLOBAL TRENDS, DOMESTIC REALITIES AND ISLAMIC LAW

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ABSTRACT

Judicial independence or independence of the judiciary has its origin in the theory of separation of powers. By this theory the Executive, the Legislature, and the Judiciary are three separate, distinct and independent branches of government; each arm is independent of the other arm in all it gets and does. As for the judiciary, the theory means both the judiciary as an institution and all individual judges presiding over cases and other personnel must be able to carry out their professional responsibilities free from any influence or interference by the Executive or Legislature or any other person or institution outside or within the judiciary. Undoubtedly, it is only an independent judiciary that can competently provide the necessary checks on the excesses of other arms of government particularly on breaches of rights and freedoms of the citizenry. This article establishes that the independence of the judiciary is an indispensable ingredient of good governance. All the international human rights conventions, the Universal Declaration on Human Rights, and other regional human rights instruments recognize the notion of independence of the judiciary in their provisions by guaranteeing the right to a fair hearing in civil and criminal proceedings before an independent and impartial court or tribunal. It also analyses judicial independence in Nigeria in line with some global trends and discovered ironically that even though the Nigerian Constitution guarantees one's rights to have one's cause heard by an independent and impartial judge, it does not guarantee institutional independence of the Nigerian judiciary at all. And this could have been the reason why the fortunes of the Nigerian judiciary are day by day dwindling as it is compelled by a lack of constitutional guarantees to always beg either the executive or the legislature for one financial favor or another. The article also analyses some of the causes of the persistent crisis in the Nigerian judiciary and also highlighted some lessons to be learnt from judicial independence under Islamic law.

KEYWORDS

Judiciary, independence, rule of law, judicial independence.

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“...there is no liberty, if the judiciary power be not separated from the legislative and executive. Were it joined with the legislative, the life and liberty of the subject would be exposed to arbitrary control; for the judge would be then the legislator. Were it joined to the executive power, the judge might behave with violence and oppression”¹

- Montesquieu

Judicial independence or independence of judiciary has its origin from the theory of separation of powers. By this theory the Executive, the Legislature and the Judiciary are three separate, distinct and independent branches of government; each arm is independent of the other arm in all it gets and does. As for the judiciary, the theory means both the judiciary as institution and all individual judges presiding over cases must be able to carry out their professional responsibilities free from any influence or interference by the Executive or Legislature or any other person or institution. It is a principle that “the judiciary should be separated from legislative and executive power, and shielded from inappropriate pressure from these branches of government, and from private or partisan interests.”² Independence of judiciary connotes complete judicial freedom in all its ramifications.

In *Valiente v. The Queen*, the Supreme Court of Canada elaborately commented on the notion of independence of judiciary as connoting:

“not only a state of mind but also a status or relationship to others – particularly to the executive branch of government – that rests on objective conditions or guarantees ...[involving] both individual and institutional relationships: the individual independence of a judge as reflected in such matters as security of tenure and the institutional independence of the court as reflected in its institutional or administrative relationships to the executive and legislative branches of government”³

So what does it take judiciary to be independent? Scholars and legal writers have for long attempted unsuccessfully to provide convincing answers as to what are the exact conditions required for judicial independence. Is this that for a judiciary to be independent it must have absolute budgetary control?⁴ Is it about its independence to choose or select its own members without interference from the executive? Or is it about the security of tenure individual judges? Is it about the decision-making and freedom to render judgements without any influence either from the executive or the legislature or the public?

McNollgast is of the view that judicial independence “is not the automatic result of constitutional or statutory provisions that establish life tenure for judges, nor is judicial independence limited by checks and balances or legal traditions”.⁵ For him judicial independence “waxes and wanes with changes in the political composition of our three branches of government.” Constitutional arrangements aside independence of judiciary is dependent upon the needs and composition of the executive and legislature at a given time. A controversial government or an undemocratic one facing many constitutional challenges does not normally allow judiciary paly its constitutional roles freely.

¹ Montesquieu, *The Spirit of the Laws*, Book XI, available at <http://www.constitution.org/cm/sol.txt> accessed on 16th February, 2013

² *Judicial Independence in Singapore*, available at http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Judicial_independence_in_Singapore accessed on 21th January, 2014

³ See (1985) 2.S.C.R *Valiente v. The Queen* 673, available at <http://scc-csc.lexum.com/decisia-scc-csc/scc-csc/scc-csc/en/item/108/index.do> accessed on 23rd Dcember, 2013

⁴ Pilar Domingo, *Judicial Independence: the Politics of the Supreme Court in Mexico*, 32 J. LATIN AMERICAN STUDIES 705 (2000)

⁵ McNollgast, *Conditions for Judicial Independence* Legal Research Paper Series, Research Paper No. 07-43, April 2006, University of San Diego School of Law) available at <http://ssrn.com/abstract=895723> accessed on 27th October, 2008

GLOBAL TREND

All the international human rights conventions, the Universal Declaration on Human Rights and other regional human rights instruments recognize the notion of independence of judiciary in their provisions by guaranteeing the right to fair hearing in civil and criminal proceedings before an independent and impartial court or tribunal. Legal scholars, international human rights organizations and human rights activists all have emphasized the potentially important role an independent judiciary can play in securing constitutionally guaranteed rights— “indeed, some assert that it is *the* indispensable link in the machinery for securing individual protection against states’ human rights abuses”.⁶

Undoubtedly, it is only an independent judiciary that can competently provide the necessary checks on the excesses of other arms of government particularly on breaches of rights and freedoms of the citizenry.

Article 14(1) of International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights states that “all persons shall be equal before the courts and tribunals” and further, that “in the determination of any criminal charge against him, or of his rights and obligations in a suit of law, *everyone shall be entitled to a fair and public hearing by a competent, independent and impartial tribunal established by law*”.

Article 10 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights stated that:

“everyone is entitled in full equality to a fair and public hearing by an independent and impartial tribunal, in the determination of his rights and obligations and of any criminal charge against him”.

In Nigeria, section 17(1)(e) of the Nigerian Constitution 1999 provides that “The independence, impartiality and integrity of Courts of Law, and easy accessibility thereto shall be secured and maintained”.

Even though some may argue that some countries may not have ratified or acceded to any of these human rights treaties and conventions, by customary international law and general principles of law, all countries in the world are bound by these treaties and general principles, whether or not they incorporate them in their municipal laws. At the Seventh United Nations Congress on the Prevention of Crime and the Treatment of Offenders, Milan, 26 August to 6 September 1985, the General Assembly adopted the Basic Principles on the Independence of the Judiciary⁷, which set forth standards for achieving independent judiciary for countries all over the world. Although the basic principles do not have a force of law, they have been recognized internationally as setting model for countries on judicial independence. And over the past two decades, there has been established trend globally for adopting these principles several countries constitutions. Many of the constitutions written after 1970s, constituting two thirds of world’s constitutions have adopted certain provisions of these principles under their bill of rights, directly or indirectly.⁸ Generally speaking, the United Nations’ basic principles on the independence of judiciary “represent a substantial degree of global consensus on what judicial independence is or should be”⁹. The principles basically cover the following issues:

- (i) Independence of the Judiciary;
- (ii) Freedom of expression and association;
- (iii) Qualifications, selection and training;
- (iv) Conditions of service and tenure;
- (v) Professional secrecy and immunity; and
- (vi) Discipline, suspension and removal.

⁶ Linda Camp Keith, *Judicial Independence and Human Rights Protection Around the World* available on <https://www.utd.edu/~lck016000/JudicatureJudicialIndependence.pdf>, accessed on 20th January, 2014

⁷ See Resolutions 40/32 of 29 November 1985 and 40/146 of 13 December 1985

⁸ Albert P. Blaustein, Gisbert H. Flanz *Constitutions of the Countries of the World* (Oceana Publications, 2002) Vol. 52

⁹ Linda Camp Keith, *supra*

Even before these principles were adopted by the UN General Assembly, the International Bar Association adopted in 1982 the IBA Minimum Standards of Judicial Independence¹⁰(New Delhi Standards) which emphasized on the principle of non-interference from either the executive or legislature into the judicial responsibilities of judiciary.

Recently, the International Association of Judicial Independence and World Peace adopted at the Mt Scopus International Standards of Judicial Independence, 2008 (as amended in 2011 and 2012). It “emphasized the importance of maintaining constitutional safeguards of judicial independence and securing judicial independence from numerous aspects”¹¹.

Globally, independence of judiciary is being viewed from two perspectives: institutional independence of the judiciary and personal/individual independence of judges in their decisions.¹²

The notion of institutional independence generally consists of:

1. Independence as to administrative matters
2. Financial independence
3. Decision-making independence
4. Jurisdictional competence

While the notion of individual independence relates to the following:

1. Appointment
2. Security of tenure
3. Financial security
4. Promotion
5. Accountability
6. Freedom of expression and association
7. Training and education

Ironically, the word “independence” was mentioned only nine times in the 1999 Constitution of Nigeria and the phrase “judicial independence” or “independence of judiciary” has never been mentioned at all. Nevertheless, under section 171(e) of the non-justiciable Chapter II in furtherance of its social order the Nigerian state shall strive to ensure the maintenance of the “independence, impartiality and integrity of courts of law and easy accessibility thereto”. It can also be argued strongly that Section 36(1) only guarantees one’s rights to have one’s cause heard by an independent and impartial judge and does not guarantee institutional independence of Nigerian judiciary at all. And this could have been the reason why the fortunes of Nigerian judiciary is day by day dwindling as it is compelled by lack of constitutional guarantees to always beg either the executive or the legislature for one financial favour or another.

The former Chief Justice of Nigeria, Hon. Justice Mariam Aloma Mukhtar had on Monday, September 23, 2013, while inaugurating the 2013/2014 Legal Year mentioned this worrisome concern when she said:

“Statistics have shown that funding from the Federal Government has witnessed a steady decline since 2010, from N95bn in that year to N85bn in 2011, then N75bn in 2012 and dropped again in the 2013 budget to N67bn. Indeed, with this, if the amount allocated to the extrajudicial organizations within the judiciary is deducted, the courts are left with a paltry sum to operate”

However, in the last two or three appropriation years the National Assembly has been engulfing over N150bn and the executive has “equally being taking good care of itself with more jets being added to the presidential

¹⁰ Available on <http://www.ibanet.org/Document/Default.aspx?DocumentUid=10917543-8f09-4a68-8324-9228bb6237a1>. Accessed on 26th January, 2014

¹¹ International Association of Judicial Independence and World Peace, available at http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/International_Association_of_Judicial_Independence_and_World_Peace accessed on 24th January, 2014

¹² *Human Rights in the Administration of Justice: A Manual on Human Rights for Judges, Prosecutors and Lawyer* available at <http://www.ohchr.org/Documents/Publications/training9chapter4en.pdf>. Accessed on 5th February, 2007

fleet and humongous amount in the neighborhood of a billion naira appropriated for meals and incidentals, yet the fortunes of Nigeria's judiciary dwindles."¹³ Of course "[t]his is preposterous!"

Even though the drafters of the 1999 Constitution introduced the National Judicial Council in good faith to secure independence of Nigerian judiciary, practically speaking for a number of reasons, political and non-political, and even constitutional, as far as budgetary allocation and control is concerned the NJC is nothing to the executive and legislature but a toothless bull dog.

Administrative independence implies that the judiciary must be able to freely handle and carry out all its administrative matters without any interference. The judiciary must be able for instance to freely assign cases to judges without interference or intervention of the executive or legislature.¹⁴

As an institution the judiciary must also be independent to render its opinion, judgments and orders free from any 'fear' of executive or legislature. For a judiciary to be independent as an institution it must garner the respect of other branches by respecting its decisions.

For the rule of law to flourish, the executive, the police, the prison and other governmental agencies must respect orders of court even if they do not agree with them. They are also duty bound to prevent erosion of the orders and decisions given by the judiciary.

Institutional independence should not only stop at the external relationship with other organs of government, but is extended to intra independence – independence of other units of the judiciary. Other judicial units of the judiciary like the magisterial districts, registries, etc must be independently carry out their official responsibilities with interference from those heading the judiciary. For instance, a chief registrar or administrative judge responsible for assigning cases must assign cases based on established rules of procedure with intervention of the chief judge or any senior judge. Institutional independence also extends to individual independence of judges to freely decide matters before him without interference from anybody included the chief judge, other senior judges and executive. This is very tasking challenge for any judge to handle. Lord Davis told us thus:

"Whatever a judge does, he will surely have his critics. If in an effort to do justice he appears to make law, there will be cries that he is overweening and that he has rendered uncertain what had been regarded as established legal principles. On the other hand, if he sticks to the old legal rules, an equally vocal body will charge him of failing to mould the law to social needs".¹⁵

THE TREND IN NIGERIA

Appointment of Judicial Officers

Under the Nigerian Constitution 1999, as far as the appointment of judicial officers is concerned the National Judicial Council is the dominant agency constitutionally responsible for making recommendations of qualified candidates to high bench at state and federal levels.¹⁶ Its recommendation for appointment by the President is subject to the confirmation of the Senate in some cases like in the case of Chief Justice of Nigeria, Justices of the Supreme Court, President of the Court of Appeal and Chief Judge of the Federal High Court, Chief Judge of the High Court of the FCT, Grand Kadis of the Sharia Court of Appeal, Abuja and President of the Customary Court of Appeal Abuja.¹⁷ Justices of the Court of Appeal, judges of the Federal High Court, judges of the High Court of FCT, Kadis of the Sharia Court of Appeal of FCT and judges of the Customary Court of Appeal of FCT are appointed by the President on simple recommendation of the NJC without approval of the Senate.¹⁸ For the appointment of Chief Judge of the state, Grand Kadi of the Sharia Court of Appeal and the President of the

¹³ Jide Ojo, *The Many travails of Nigerian Judiciary*, Punch, October, 9th 2013 available at <http://www.punchng.com/opinion/the-many-travails-of-nigerian-judiciary/> accessed on 12th January, 2013

¹⁴ Principle 14 of the Basic Principles

¹⁵ In *Judicial Activism: Current Legal problems* (1975), culled from Aluko A. O. "The Doctrine of Stare Descisis and the Nigerian Legal System: A Theoretical Perspective," LASU Journal Vol iii (1998) page 23

¹⁶ Section 1, Part 1 of the Third Schedule to the 1999 Constitution

¹⁷ Sections 231(1);(2); 238(1); 250(1); 261(1) and 266(1) all of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria

¹⁸ Sections 238(2); 250(2); 256(2); 261(2) and 266(2) all of the 1999 Constitution of Federal Republic of Nigeria

Customary Court, the Governor shall make the appointment on the recommendation of the NJC subject to the confirmation of the House of Assembly.

It is to be noted that in Nigeria like in many countries, majority of the judicial officers at both state and federal levels are surprisingly being appointed by the executive – governor of a state or the President. It can be argued that appointment by the executive does not in itself raise any doubt about the independence of judiciary of a country or of a particular judge concerned.

In New Zealand for instance, Justices of the Supreme Court, Court of Appeal and judges of High Court, are appointed by the Governor-General on the recommendation of the Attorney-General advised by the Chief Justice and the Solicitor-General. For appointments to district courts, the Governor-General is advised by the Attorney-General who receives advice from the Chief District Court Judge and the Secretary for Justice.¹⁹

In the United States, all Article III Judges, i.e Justices of the Supreme Court and Court of Appeals and district judges are appointed to office by the President of the United States, with the approval of the U.S Senate. And traditionally, Presidents “most often appoint judges who are members, or at least generally supportive, of their political party”²⁰ – however, that doesn’t mean that judges are given appointments solely for partisan reasons.

In Canada, a federation consisting of a central government and 10 provinces and 3 territories appointment of judicial officers to both superior (federal) and provincial or territorial courts are being made by Governor General (appointed by the Prime Minister) to represent Canadian Monarch who currently is Queen Elizabeth II. All federal justices and judges including justices of the Supreme Court of Canada and federal Court of Appeal are being appointed by Governor General on the recommendation of the federal cabinet.²¹

In Malaysia all judges are appointed by the Monarch acting on advice of the Prime Minister.²²

In Italy and South Korea, 1/3 of members of the constitutional court is appointed by the president, 1/3 by the legislature, and 1/3 by the supreme court. (One variant has 1/3 appointed by each of two houses of the legislature and 1/3 by the chief executive.)²³

A different pattern of appointment i.e. self-appointing practice is in India, where members of the higher bench are being appointed by the President after consultation with the Supreme Court.

In United States each state has its own state judiciary, including the Supreme Court. There are varied strange patterns of appointment that evolved over time. Generally, for appointment to the high court, there is a pattern in about eight states i.e Alabama, Illinois, Louisiana, New Mexico, New York, Pennsylvania, Texas, West Virginia by which judges run on a party ticket as republicans or democrats and get appointed on that platform. Thereafter, they run for uncontested non-partisan elections to retain their offices. And in Arkansas, Georgia, Idaho, Kentucky, Michigan, Minnesota, Mississippi, Montana, Nevada, North Carolina, North Dakota, Ohio, Oregon, Washington, Wisconsin judges are initially appointed on merit and years after they run for an election to retain their offices on the basis of their judicial record.²⁴In 1986 three Justices of the Supreme Court of California were recalled because of their vocal opposition to death penalty.

Just like in Japan, where judges of the lower bench are appointed by the Supreme Court, but will be subjected to election by public every ten years.²⁵

It appears there are good lessons that the Nigerian judiciary could learn from states in the US and from Japanese. If our judges of superior courts know very well that upon their initial appointments they have to run for elections, not even necessarily under the PDP or CAN or APGA, to retain their offices based on their

¹⁹ See New Zealand Judicial Appointment Protocol 2013 available at http://www.crownlaw.govt.nz/artman/docs/cat_index_6.asp accessed on 23rd January, 2014

²⁰ See How the Federal Courts are Organised: Federal Judges and How they Get Appointed, available at <http://www.fjc.gov/federal/courts.nsf/autoframe?OpenForm&nav=menu3c&page=/federal/courts.nsf/page/A783011AF949B6BF85256B35004AD214?opendocument> accessed on 13th September, 2013

²¹ See Judges Act R.S.C., 1985, c. J-1; last

²² Article 122B (1) of the Federal Constitution

²³ Judicial Appointments and Judicial Independence (a United States Institute of Peace document) available on www.usip.org accessed on 14th January, 2014

²⁴ See ABA Fact Sheet on Judicial Selection Methods in The States, available at http://www.americanbar.org/content/dam/aba/migrated/leadership/fact_sheet.authcheckdam.pdf, accessed on 12th January, 2013

²⁵ See Article 79 of the Constitution of Japan

integrity, honesty and dedication to work, majority could have changed their attitude. Of course there could be the tendency of manipulating the electorate and tremendous influence and interference of the ruling party as usual. Studies in the US have shown that "seventy-six percent (76%) of voters, and 26 percent of state judges, believe that campaign contributions made to judges have at least some influence on their decisions"²⁶. Of course even in the US studies have shown that there has been a feeling in about 62% of voters and including nearly 90 percent of African-American voters— ...that "there are two systems of justice in the U.S.—one for the rich and powerful and one for everyone else"²⁷.

Cumulatively therefore, it is not strange that in Nigeria, just like in Russia, US and Brazil that appointments of the superior courts judges and justices are being made by the executive. There is no doubt that the NJC is established by the Constitution to ensure independence of the judicial officers even from their appointment and to minimize executive interference, influence and manipulation. Nevertheless, its composition has been subject to a number of scornful criticisms. It has been argued that the composition of NJC has grossly violate principle of federalism,²⁸ is full of federal dominance and states have not been given any role to play in the appointment Chief Judges for their respective states.²⁹

So which of the selection processes is the best? There is no consensus as to which of the selection process is the best. Each process is entirely dependent on the country's culture, political set up and enlightenment and constitutional history. What works for one country may not necessarily work for another country.

The trend for selection globally leans towards a very widely publicized and transparent mechanism, which involves wide advertisement of judicial vacancies, publicity of candidates' names, backgrounds, qualifications etc. It is also best practice globally that the public are invited to comment on the shortlisted candidates. The judicial councils should also composed not only judicial officers but other actors like lawyers, law professors, judges of inferior courts so as to enhance the quality of the selection and minimize possible influence from the executive or partisan selection from other judicial officers in the council or even influence by the chief justice or other senior judges. In some countries like Georgia and Chile, even before nominating candidates to judicial council, transparent examination is being conducted. When a candidate passes the exam his name is then submitted to the council for further verification and public tests.³⁰Diversity is also something to be considered during judicial selection. A judiciary that reflects the diversity of its country "is more likely to garner public confidence".³¹Nevertheless, under section 288(1) of the 1999 Constitution of Federal Republic of Nigeria the President is enjoined while appointing justices of the Supreme Court and the Court of Appeal to have regard to the need to ensure there are among them persons learned in Islamic personal law and persons learned in Customary law.

Generally speaking, there is no guidance internationally as to the way selection of judicial officers it to be made. The most important is that regardless of the selection process, persons to be appointed judges professional qualifications and personal integrity should always constitute the criteria for the selection.³²

Finally, it is to be noted however, that in countries where politicians are making judicial appointments, the trend leans more towards accountability in the judicial affairs rather than total independence of the judiciary.

Security of Tenure:

This is the notion that once appointed; a judge cannot be removed during his term of office except for good cause i.e unethical or unprofessional conduct, unfitness upon following formal proceedings or hearing. A judge who can be removed at any time is naturally vulnerable to both external and internal pressures to do what is wrong. In some countries, like in France and Germany, not only that a judge cannot be removed without

²⁶ Facts and Stats, available on http://www.justiceatstake.org/resources/facts_stats_and_quotes/facts_stats.cfm accessed on 11th January, 2014

²⁷ *ibid*;

²⁸ J. O. Akande, Introduction to The 1999 Nigerian Constitution (Lagos: NIJ Professional Publishers, 2001) at 496 – 49

²⁹ D. A. Ijalaye, The Imperatives of Federal/ State Relations in a Fledging Democracy/Implications for Nigeria (Lagos: NIALS, 2001) 9

³⁰ See *Guidance for Promoting Judicial Independence and Impartiality* (Office of Democracy and Governance, USAID, 2002) pp. 16 - 18 available on <http://www.usaid.gov/democracy/> accessed on 14th December, 2006

³¹ *ibid*, pg. 19

³² See Principle 10 of the Basic Principles

decision of court, no judge can even be transferred or promoted without his consent. Security of tenure of judicial officers in Nigeria is a matter of constitution and is covered under sections 291 and 292.

292. (1) A judicial officer shall not be removed from his office or appointment before his age of retirement except in the following circumstances -

(a) in the case of -

(i) Chief Justice of Nigeria, President of the Court of Appeal, Chief Judge of the Federal High Court, Chief Judge of the High Court of the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Grand Kadi of the Sharia Court of Appeal of the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja and President, Customary Court of Appeal of the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, by the President acting on an address supported by two-thirds majority of the Senate.

(ii) Chief Judge of a State, Grand Kadi of a Sharia Court of Appeal or President of a Customary Court of Appeal of a State, by the Governor acting on an address supported by two-thirds majority of the House of Assembly of the State, praying that he be so removed for his inability to discharge the functions of his office or appointment (whether arising from infirmity of mind or of body) or for misconduct or contravention of the Code of Conduct;

(b) in any case, other than those to which paragraph (a) of this subsection applies, by the President or, as the case may be, the Governor acting on the recommendation of the National Judicial Council that the judicial officer be so removed for his inability to discharge the functions of his office or appointment (whether arising from infirmity of mind or of body) or for misconduct or contravention of the Code of Conduct.

The above section doesn't in any way provide the necessary security of tenure to Nigerian judicial officers based on the best practices globally. In light of realities of the global trends on security of tenure of judicial officers, the shallowness of section 292 of the 1999 Constitution is surprising. It literally left the mechanism for removing judicial officers on the hands of politicians. All that the section requires the President or the Governor to do is to garner 2/3 political support in the Senate or House of Assembly for an ordinary letter stating that the judicial officer be removed for misconduct or contravention of Code of Conduct, inability to discharge his functions as a result of infirmity of mind etc.

The most surprising constitutional defect of the section 292 is that it does not at all provide any opportunity to the judicial officer to be removed to defend himself or by a legal practitioner of his own choice. It does not contemplate a hearing at all, either before the President or the Governor as the case may be makes his political address before the Senate or the House of Assembly. This is a clear dreadful breach of section 36 of the 1999 Constitution guaranteeing right to fair hearing. Constitution against itself! It is calamitous too find this arrangement in the constitution of the Federal republic of Nigeria, especially as it relates to the offices of highly placed judicial officers like the Chief Justice of Nigeria, Chief Judges of States etc.

Surprisingly however, the constitutional arrangement for the removal of judicial officers in Nigeria under sections 276 and 277 of the 1989 Constitution of Federal Republic of Nigeria was much more in line with global best practices. One step forward, ten steps backward!

Under section 276 of the 1989 Constitution the Chief Justice of Nigeria could not be removed from office except by the president acting on an address supported by 2/3rd majority of the Senate "praying that he be so removed for his inability to discharge the functions of his office or appointment (whether arising from infirmity of body or mind) or for misconduct or for the contravention of the code of conduct". The allegation for misconduct against the Chief Justice of Nigeria by the President or against Chief Judge of a state by the Governor must be made in writing addressed to the President of the Senate or Speaker of House of Representatives in the case of the Chief Justice of Nigeria or Speaker House of Assembly who shall constitute "a panel to be called the Investigating Panel; consisting of five members, all of whom shall be persons of unquestionable integrity and two of who shall be non members of the Legal Profession to investigate the allegations".³³ If the allegation is not established after investigation, "no further proceedings shall be taken in respect of this matter".³⁴ A person can only be a member of the panel if in the case of the Chief Justice of Nigeria, he has served as Chief Justice of Nigeria, Justice of the Supreme Court or he is a legal practitioner and

³³ Section 276(2) of 1989 Constitution

³⁴ Section 276 (3) of 1989 Constitution

who has been so qualified for a period of not less than 15 years”.³⁵ And the case of removal of Chief Judge of a state, a member must have served as Chief Justice of Nigeria, Justice of the Supreme court, President or Justice of the Court of Appeal, Chief Judge or Judge of High Court of a State, Grand Khadi or Kadi of Sharia Court of Appeal or president or Judge of the Customary Court or he is a Leal Practitioner and has been so qualified for a period of not less than 12 years. It should be noted that, the chairman of the panel in case of Chief Justice of Nigeria must be “a person who has served as Chief justice of Nigeria or who is a legal practitioner and who has been so qualified for a period of 15 years”. In the case of Chief Judge of a state the chairman of the panel must be “a person who has served as Chief Justice of Nigeria, Justice of the Supreme Court, President or Justice of the Court of Appeal, a Chief Judge or Legal Practitioner of not less than 12 years”.

A very interesting insertion under section 276 of 1989 Constitution as against the shallow provision of section 292 of the 1999 Constitution is the opportunity given to the Chief Justice or Judge against whom an allegation of inability to misconduct or contravention of the code of conduct has been made “to defend himself in person or by a legal practitioner of his own choice before the investigating panel”.³⁶ After the investigation, the panel shall submit its findings/report to the President of the Senate or Speaker of House of Representatives or Speaker House of Assembly as the case may be who shall “immediately submit the said report to the Senate or the House of Assembly for consideration”.³⁷ Within 60 days of the receipt of the report, the Senate or House of Assembly shall consider the report and if considered and confirmed by an address supported by two thirds majority of the Senate or House of Assembly as the case may be, the Senate President in case of removal of Chief Justice of Nigeria or Speaker House of Assembly “shall send the decision thereof to the President or the Governor of the State who shall thereupon remove the Chief Justice of Nigeria or the Chief Judge of a state from his office, as the case may be”.³⁸ What a transparent stringent mechanism!

Even for the removal of justices of the Supreme Court, Court of Appeal and judges or Chief Judge of Federal High Court by the President the 1989 Constitution under section 277 stipulates an address of the President acting on recommendation of the Federal Judicial Service Commission to be supported by 2/3 majority of Senate acting on recommendation of the Federal Judicial Service Commission.³⁹ The same prescription applies mutatis mutandis for the removal of high court judges, Grand Kadi and Kadis of Sharia Court of Appeal, judges and President of the Customary Court of Appeal. Also there must be an allegation in writing to the head of the respective judicial service commission who shall thereafter constitute a panel of four members of persons of unquestionable character. The procedure then follows mutatis mutandis the procedure followed for the removal of Chief Justice of Nigeria or Chief Judge of a state under section 276.⁴⁰ Further, to ensure quick dispensation of the procedure for removal of judicial officers of superior courts in Nigeria sub section 8 of section 277 disallowed all courts in Nigeria from entertaining or determining any issue pending before the investigations panel or the Senate or House of Assembly on removal of Chief Justice of Nigeria or other justices or judges of the superior courts.

From the above it can be clearly understood even though the 1989 Constitution did not see the light of the day and was made under the military, the mechanisms for removing superior judicial officers was by far more in line to best practices than the one under the 1999 Constitution. Although no statistics are available for the number of Chief Judges and judges of the high courts removed after the coming of the 1999 Constitution, the everyday reports on removing judges especially of high court is alarming.

It is to be submitted that in jurisdictions where there is stringent and transparent impeachment procedure after a trial, judges are more confident and independent because they cannot deliver a decision today and wake up tomorrow just to find out on dailies they are removed in the night. In the United States of America in the last

³⁵ Section 276 (4) of the 1989 Constitution

³⁶ Section 276 (5) 1989 Constitution

³⁷ Section 276 (6) 1989 Constitution

³⁸ Section 276 (7)(8) and (9) 1989 Constitution

³⁹ Section 277 (1) 1989 Constitution

⁴⁰ See section 277 91) – (7) of the 1989 Constitution

222 years, only “fifteen federal judges have been impeached. Of those fifteen: eight were convicted by the Senate, four were acquitted by the Senate, and three resigned before an outcome at trial.”⁴¹

In the last 222 years America has only 17 Chief Justice, while Nigeria had 12 in the last 53 years. In the last 222 years America had only 112 Justices of the Supreme Court and Nigeria has had 95 in 57 years.⁴² Nigerians still remember the case of Chief Judge of Kwara State, Justice Raliat Elelu-Habeeb, who removed in 2009 the questionable procedure only to be reinstated by Supreme Court in 2012⁴³ and number of judges and justices are being investigated by NJC.⁴⁴

FINANCIAL INDEPENDENCE

Funding judiciary in Nigeria is matter provided for by the 1999 Constitution. The Constitution has recognized directly and indirectly financial autonomy of the judicial arm in very clear terms. In fact funding the Nigerian judiciary is granted the status of “first line charge” by the Constitution. Section 84(1)(2) of the Constitution provides:

There shall be paid to the holders of the offices mentioned in this section such remuneration, salaries and allowances as may be prescribed by the National Assembly, but not exceeding the amount as shall have been determined by the Revenue Mobilization Allocation and Fiscal Commission.

(2) The remuneration, salaries and allowances payable to the holders of the offices so mentioned shall be a charge upon the Consolidated Revenue Fund of the Federation.

(3) The remuneration and salaries payable to the holders of the said offices and their conditions of service, other than allowances, shall not be altered to their disadvantage after their appointment.

(4) The offices aforesaid are the offices of President, Vice-President, Chief Justice of Nigeria, Justice of the Supreme Court, President of the Court of Appeal, Justice of the Court of Appeal, Chief Judge of the Federal High Court, Judge of the Federal High Court, Chief Judge and Judge of the High Court of the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Chief Judge of a State, Judge of the High Court of a State, Grand Kadi of the Sharia Court of Appeal of the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, President and Judge of the Customary Court of Appeal of the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Grand Kadi and Kadi of the Sharia Court of Appeal of a State, President and Judge of the Customary Court of Appeal of a State...

The Supreme Court of Nigeria in *A.G. Federation v. A.G. Abia State & Ors* held that ^[15]“It is the Consolidated Revenue Fund of the Federation and not the Federation Account that is charged with the salaries of Judicial Officers in the Federation.”⁴⁵

Furthermore, section 81(1) provides:

Any amount standing to the credit of the judiciary in the Consolidated Revenue Fund of the Federation shall be “paid directly to the National Judicial Council for disbursement to the heads of the courts established for the Federation and the State under section 6 of this Constitution.”

Section 121(3) also provides that “any amount standing to the credit of the judiciary in the Consolidated Revenue Fund of the State shall be paid directly to the heads of the courts concerned”.

The Table below can literally shed more light on whether the funding of Nigerian judiciary is dwindling day by day.⁴⁶

⁴¹ Judgepedia at http://judgepedia.org/Impeachment_of_federal_judges accessed on 29th January, 2014

⁴² A case for Elongation of Tenure of Nigerian Judges, available on <http://www.channelkoos.com/index.php/features/301-a-case-for-elongation-of-tenure-of-nigerian-judges>, accessed on 19th January, 2014

⁴³ Daily Times Nigeria, of 18th February, 2012 <http://www.dailytimes.com.ng/article/supreme-court-reinstates-elelu-habeeb-kwaras-chief-judge>

⁴⁴ Premium Times of 18th July, 2013, available on <http://premiumtimesng.com/metro/141267-njc-indicts-ex-abuja-chief-judge-gummi-for-undue-judicial-interference.html> accessed on 12th January, 2014

⁴⁵ (2002) 6 NWLR (Prt 764) 542 at 688

⁴⁶ *ibid*; Sourced from Prof. Azinge’s paper. Generally analyse the Appropriation Acts from 2004-2013; see Prof. E Azinge SAN, *Courts Budget: Implications for Access to Justice* a paper delivered 17th April, 2013 at Commonwealth Law Conference, Cape Town, South Africa available on [http://www.nials-nigeria.org/Editedbookcovers/COURTS%20AND%20BUDGET%20BY%20PROF%20AZINGE%20SAN%20\(1\).pdf](http://www.nials-nigeria.org/Editedbookcovers/COURTS%20AND%20BUDGET%20BY%20PROF%20AZINGE%20SAN%20(1).pdf) accessed on 12th May, 2013

Y YEAR YE	ALLOCATION TO NJC	TOTAL BUDGET IN NAIRA	PERCENTAGE TO NJC
200 2004	30,000,000,000	1,302,523,844,588.00	2.3%
2005	33,000,000,000	1,799,938,243,138.00	1.8%
2006	35,000,000,000	1,899,987,922,467	1.8%
2007	43,000,000,000	2,266,394,423,477	1.8%
2008	78,000,000,000	2,647,492,865,643	2.9%
2009	78,000,000,000.	2,870,510,042,679	2.7%
2010	91,000,000,000	4,079,654,724,257	2.2%
2011	95,000,000,000	4,226,191,559,259	2.2%
2012	85,000,000,000	4,749,100,821,170	1.7%
2013	67,000,000,000	4,924,604,000,000	1.3%

From the above illustration one can see how the institutional independence of Nigerian judiciary is corroding and crumbling year after year by the disproportionate treatment judiciary gets through conspiracy between the executive and legislature. The negative implication of this doesn't stop at the judiciary as an institution; it is more detrimental and injurious to a common man than to the judiciary itself. This is because "all the rights secured to the citizens under the Constitution are worth nothing, and a mere bubble, except guaranteed to them by an independent and virtuous Judiciary."⁴⁷ A poor-funded judiciary breeds poor members, intellectually and rationally who do not care about efficiency, honesty or integrity. The poor state of Nigerian judiciary and its catalogue of disclosed and undisclosed unprofessional allegations, corruption, bribery and judgment procurement is not unconnected with its poor funding; so also the poor performance of some of the judges at state and federal level. Charles Evans Hughes told us that:

"A poor Judge [in terms of integrity] is perhaps the most wasteful indulgence of the community. You can refuse to patronize a merchant who does not carry good stock, but you have no recourse if you are haled before a Judge whose mental or moral goods are inferior. An honest..., able and fearless Judge is the most valuable servant of democracy, for he illuminates justice as he interprets and applies the law"⁴⁸

Oscar Wilde puts this bitter truth further succinctly when he said:

"As for the virtuous poor, one can pity them, of course, but one cannot possibly admire them. They have made private terms with the enemy, and sold their birthright for very bad pottage. They must also be extraordinarily stupid."⁴⁹

The situation is even worse in the state judiciary as pointed out by the former Chief Justice of Nigeria, Hon. Justice Dahiru Musdapher when he said:

"It is regrettable that some state chief executives treat the judiciary as an appendage of the executive arm...The plight of the state judiciaries is compounded by the fact that, in spite of the best efforts of the NJC, the processes of appointment and removal of Judges/security of tenure is the subject of political theatrics."⁵⁰

⁴⁷ Andres Jackson, Brainy Quotes, available at <http://www.brainyquote.com/quotes/quotes/a/andrewjack401401.html> accessed on 23rd January, 2014

⁴⁸ Charles Evans Hughes, quoted in Itse Sagay: Recent Trends in the Status and Practice of the Rule of Law (Ibadan: ASUU Press, 1988), pg. 36

⁴⁹Oscar Wilde(1854-1900) Irish poet and dramatist; in "*The Soul of Man*" <http://en.proverbia.net/citastema.asp?tematica=925&page=6>

JUDICIAL INDEPENDENCE IN JAPAN

“Japanese judges are among the most honest, politically independent and professionally competent in the world today.”⁵¹

In Japan just like in Nigeria, judges are public servants. However unlike in Nigeria, in Japan people and choose and remove judges. Article 15 of the Japan Constitution provides:

“The people have the inalienable right to choose their public officials and to dis- miss them. All public officials are servants of the whole community and not of any group thereof. Universal adult suffrage is guaranteed with regard to the election of public officials. In all elections, secrecy of the ballot shall not be violated. A voter shall not be answerable, publicly or privately, for the choice he has made.”

The apex court in Japan is the Supreme Court (Saikō saibansho) presided by 15 Justices 6 of whom are former career judges and the remaining Justices are without regular career as judges at all. Just like in Nigeria, the Supreme Court of Japan is the highest constitutional court and the last resort of all Japanese people. A very unique feature of Japanese judicial system is that even lower courts can determine constitution questions and that the Supreme Court can hear appeals in all cases, except cases decided summarily by lower courts.⁵² And because the Supreme Court does not have control over its docket, it decides over 4000 cases every year – civil and criminal. On average a Justice of the Supreme Court of Japan decides about 1,300 cases annually.⁵³

By convention, at least at least 1/3 of all Supreme Court Justices are appointed from mainstream judiciary and 1/3 from the bar and up to five of the fifteen justices other persons of "attainment in their profession with knowledge of law. The Chief Justice is nominated by the cabinet and appointed by the Emperor. The Chief Justice is accorded the same rank and salary as the prime minister and other justice are appointed by the cabinet has equal rank and salary as ministers of state.⁵⁴ Interestingly, nineteen out of thirty-nine lawyers who have served on the Court, were former bar association presidents or vice presidents.

As of July 2010, six out of the fifteen justices, are career judges, four were attorneys, two were public prosecutors, two were public servants (one from the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, and the other from the Ministry of Public Welfare and Labor), and one is a former law professor and judge.⁵⁵

By Article 78 of the Japanese Constitution, judges shall not be removed except by public impeachment unless judicially declared mentally or physically incompetent to perform official duties. No disciplinary action against judges shall be administered by any executive organ or agency. The appointment of the judges of the Supreme Court shall be reviewed by Japanese people at the first general election of members of the House of Representatives following their appointment, and shall be reviewed again at the first general election of members of the House of Representatives after a lapse of ten(10)years, and in the same manner thereafter.⁵⁶ Another manner of removing judges in Japan is by impeachment by an impeachment court/committee consisting of twenty members 10 from House of Representatives and 10 from House of Councilors (Diet).⁵⁷ Impeachment

⁵⁰ Hon. Justice Dahiru Musdapher, *The Nigerian Judiciary: Towards reform of the Bastion of Constitutional Democracy* (Institute of Advanced Legal Studies, 2011) available at <http://nials-nigeria.org/pub/THE%20NIGERIAN%20JUDICIARY%20Towards%20Reform%20Of%20The%20Baston%20Of%20Constitutional%20Democracy.pdf> accessed on 11th January, 2014

⁵¹ John O. Haley, *The Japanese Judiciary: Maintaining Integrity, Autonomy and the Public Trust* Wiley B. Rutledge Professor of Law Washington University in St. Louis, available at <http://law.wustl.edu/harris/documents/2003-3HaleyJapaneseJudiciary.pdf>, accessed on 24th January, 2014

⁵² Takayuki Li, Japanese Way of Judicial Appointment and Its Impact on Judicial Review available on <http://www.law.ntu.edu.tw/ntulawreview/articles/5-2/03-Article-Takayuki%20Li.pdf> accessed on 12th February, 2013

⁵³ *ibid*; John O. Haley

⁵⁴ See Article 41 of the Court Organization Law 1947

⁵⁵ Yuichiro Tsuji, Independence of the Judiciary and Judges in Japan, available at [http://www.surugadai.ac.jp/sogo/media/bulletin/Hougaku24-03/Hougaku.24-3.\(63\).pdf](http://www.surugadai.ac.jp/sogo/media/bulletin/Hougaku24-03/Hougaku.24-3.(63).pdf) accessed on 23rd December, 2013

⁵⁶ See Article 79 of the Japanese Constitution

⁵⁷ <http://web-japan.org/links/government/diet/diet.html>

of judge needs 2/3 of members of the impeachment court. A judge can be impeached for clear breach of professional duties or extreme neglect of his duties or any misconduct resulting loss of honour and authority as a judge. There is no appeal from the decision of impeachment committee.

JUDICIAL INDEPENDENCE UNDER ISLAMIC LAW

Appointment of judges in Sharia is being done objectively and independently by the head of government based on merit or by election by group of prominent scholars. This is to ensure that upon appointment judges are independent of the government that appoints them.⁵⁸ Abu Dhar reported thus:

“I said to the Prophet (PBUH) O, messenger of Allah, will not you appoint me to a public office? The Prophet (PBUH) stroke my shoulder with his hand and said, “O, Abu Dhar, You are weak and this responsibility is a trust, on the Day of Judgment, it will be a cause of loss of honour and ignominy except for those people who will have accepted it with all the responsibilities attached to it and would have fulfilled those responsibilities properly”⁵⁹

One very unique feature of judiciary in Islam is its independence. In Islam, judicial rulings, decisions and interpretations are based on Quran and Sunnah of the Holy prophet (SAW). This guarantees that the rulings and decisions would be quite accurate, precise and perfect free from personal whims of the individual judges. And this also means that decisions and interpretations as opposed to other legal systems are going to be uniform and the same all over Islamic state and would continue for generations. And for this reason therefore judges under Islamic Sharia are further enjoined pass down their decisions without any discrimination between the rulers and the ruled, rich or poor, old or young. Deciding cases based on social status, political affiliation or influence is not only unethical and wrong in Sharia but is a crime and deviation from Allah. The Holy Prophet (SAW) was reported to have said:

"Judges are of three types, two of whom will be in Hell and one in Paradise: a man who judges unjustly and knowingly will be in Hell; a judge who has no knowledge and destroys people's rights will be in Hell; and a judge who judges in accordance with the truth will be in Paradise".⁶⁰

It should be noted however, that even though judicial decisions in Sharia must be based on Quran and Sunnah, the judge himself is encouraged to exercise *ijtihad* (independent reasoning) on issues without clear reference from Quran, Sunnah, analogy or consensus of Islamic jurists.

The Holy Prophet was reported have said:

"When a judge gives a decision, having tried his best to decide correctly and is right, there are two rewards for him; and if he gives a judgment after having tried his best (to reach a correct decision) but erred, there is one reward for him"⁶¹

Judges under Sharia must also be paid adequate salary in order to prevent them from taking gifts or bribe.

The Prophet (peace be upon him) said:

"Whoso from you is appointed by us to a position of authority and we gave him fees, what he takes more than that would be misappropriation (of public funds)"⁶²

A judge in Sharia as opposed to other legal system is not only a judicial officer but also religious officer and his authority included performing other functions and duties not purely judicial because of his knowledge of Islamic law. These include performing prayers at mosque, supervising religious places, taking custody of missing funds, missing persons, supervising pilgrimage, delivering Friday sermons etc.⁶³ Shams-al-Din Ibn Tulun told us Taj-

⁵⁸ Al-Kindi: *Al-Wulah wa Al-Qudah*, p 433

⁵⁹ (Sahih Muslim, hadith book)

⁶⁰ Narrated by Al-Tirmizi, book "judgments" p.1322, Abu Dawud (3573), and Ibn Majah (2315). Al-Albani said the hadith is correct; review: Sahih Al-Jami (4447)

⁶¹ Narrated by Al-Bukhari : Book of judgments (6919), and Muslim: Book of judicial decisions (15)

⁶² Narrated by Abu Dawud on the authority of Buraydah ibn Al-Hasib: Book "Tribute", Spoils, and Leadership (2943)

⁶³ Ibn Kathir: *Al-Bidayah wa Al-Nihayah* 13/380

al-Din Al-Subki one of prominent judges of Damascus, was a judge, taught in school, delivered Friday sermons at Tulun mosque, gave fatwas at Da-al-Adl (the house of justice) etc.⁶⁴

Independence of judiciary was clearly demonstrated when Ibn Kathir in his *Al-Bidayah wa Alnihaya* mentioned a very interesting story of a suit filed against a Christian by Ali (RA). He stated that Ali ibn Abu Talib (may Allah be pleased with him) lost a he liked so much and it was discovered in the hands of a Christian trying to sell it in a Kufa market. Ali took the man to Judge Shurayh and sued him over the shield. The following transpired in court:

Ali said: "This is my shield." Shurayh said to the Christian man: "What is your answer?" The man answered: "No, this is my shield." Ali replied: "No, it is mine since I never sold or gave it to any one." The man said that he did not accuse Ali of lying, but he said the shield was his, as it was in his hands. Shurayh turned to Ali saying: "I believe you, but we need the statement of two witnesses to back your story." Ali laughed and said: "Shurayh is right, and I have no evidence." So, Shurayh judged that the shield was the man's. As the Christian man took the shield and left, he returned and said: "O Ali, the shield is yours. What a great religion! I can sue Ali and get a judge to pass a decision for my benefit! I declare myself a Muslim"

Under the Islamic law judges are expected to be just and to administer the law as ordained by Allah without giving any regard to the parties social status or political position. Al Sayuti in his *Tarikh Al-Khulafa* (the history of caliphs) also mentioned another story demonstrating full independence of judiciary under Islamic Law. He said that there was a land dispute between a marchant and a commander of the Caliph Jaafar al Mansur. Caliph Jaafar Al-Mansur wrote a letter to the judge of Basra Swar ibn Abdullah requesting him to henceforth confiscate the piece of land and deliver the title to his commander. Swar wrote back to Caliph that the said land belonged to the merchant not the commander and he could not confiscate anything which by evidence was established to belong to someone. When the Caliph insisted upon his request and without success he said: "By Allah, I spread justice, and my judges guided me to the right".

Under Islamic law judges can summon caliphs and governors for testimonies or to defend cases filed against them. In one incident porters of Madina filed an action against Caliph Jaafar al Mansur who wanted to eject them to Levant. The case came before Muhammad ibn Imran Al-Talhi jdge of Madina. The caliph was summoned. The judge warned his secretary not to call the Caliph with his title but with his ordinary name a party to the suit. When the Caliph arrived the court ibn Imran did not stand up to welcome him. At the end of the suit, judgement was given in favourt of the porters i.e against the Caliph. It is at the end o fthe proceedings that inb Imran greeted the Caliph. Al-Mansur was happy with the conduct of the judge and granted him Ten Thousand Dinars.⁶⁵

The Supreme Court of Pakistan observed in the case of *Al-Jehad Trust v Federation of Pakistan* PLD 1996 SC 324, at 424 that

"Upon the advent of Islam, judicial functions were separated from the executive func- tions at its very initial stage. [...] The reason being that the foundation of Islam is justice. The concept of justice in Islam is different from the concept of the remedial justice of the Greeks, the natural justice of the Romans or the formal justice of the Anglo-Saxons. Jus- tice in Islam seeks to attain a higher standard of what we may call 'absolute justice' or 'absolute fairness'"

THE CRISIS IN NIGERIAN JUDICIARY

Mere googling the phrase "crisis in Nigerian judiciary" will send a message that all is not well in Nigerian judiciary. The result is extraordinarily revealing of the so many crisis bedeviling our courts, our judges and other officers of courts ranging from demanding or accepting bribes, judgement procurement to some light unethical practices of being partisan.

⁶⁴ Shams-al-Din ibn Tulun: Qudat Dimashq (the judges of Damascus), p104.

⁶⁵ Alsuyuti, ibid, 229

One of the shocking reports is from the Nigerian Tribune (online) of 26th August, 2011. The report is titled “*FG uncovers corruption in judiciary – N106 bn traced to judgement procurement- judges own luxury houses in UK, UAE, S/Africa*”.⁶⁶ The paper claimed to base its findings on a ‘secret report’ submitted to the federal government “which indicted a number of judicial officers of monumental corruption”. The paper alleges that according to investigations some properties were bought globally especially in Dubai, UAE, South Africa and London and the real owners were believed to be Nigerian judicial officers whose total emoluments cannot in anyway justify the purchases. The report further stated, a source privy to the paper informed them that some of the judicial officers were “found to send their children to some of the most expensive schools in the world, without taking loans.”⁶⁷

During a 2 day workshop on the rule of law organized by the NBA the CJN, Hon. Justice Mariam Aloma Mukhtar had in May 2013 said that “21 judges are being investigated for alleged breaches of principles of the Code of Conduct for Judicial Officers, in the on-going efforts of the National Judicial Council (NJC) at overhauling and reforming the judiciary”.⁶⁸

Another disturbing story appeared on the Vanguard of 4th January 2014 captioned “EFCC Moves to Prosecute Seven Corrupt Judges”.⁶⁹ The most disturbing is that “suspected judges are from the State and Federal High courts as well as the Court of Appeal”.⁷⁰

Of course one may find it difficult to ascertain the authenticity of some of these reports. Nevertheless, objectively speaking, even if these reports contain some doubtful facts and speculations, the allegations ought to be investigated in a very transparent way so that the public will know what really is happening. This is because in a transparent society, media reports like this one are like canary songs. Coal miners used to carry caged canaries into the mines with them. When the canaries stopped singing, they knew they were in trouble and they had better get out fast. The media in government and other large organizations are, in a way, our canaries. When they are free to ‘sing,’ those institutions are healthy. When they are silenced, we are in trouble.

It should be noted however; the crises in Nigerian judiciary are prominent because of two things. For the importance of judiciary the crises in it could be more devastating than crises in other arms of government. It is just like having ‘crises’ in the most important part of one’s body – the heart. The crises in judiciary are prominent because ordinarily, as Nigerians’ ‘watchdog’ the judiciary is not supposed to be in crises. People talk about it because the judiciary supposed to intervene when other arms are in crises. Nigerians talk about it because other arms, with all due respect, have always been in crises of some sort.

Logically and even constitutionally, Nigerians always expect other arms of government to be in crises and always expect the judiciary to determine the crises and declare who is right and who is wrong.

The big question then remains thus: how can Nigerians have a crises-free judiciary?

Nigerians can have crises-free judiciary when the government ensures the implementation of constitutional arrangements guaranteeing independence of judiciary. Nigerian judiciary can be crises-free when the government ensures full implementation of all the principles in the international instruments guaranteeing ‘inalienable right’ of judiciary to be independent - like the Basic Principles on the Independence of the judiciary 1985, like the Basic Principles on the Role of Lawyers, 1990. Nnaemeka-Agu:

“What cannot be doubted is that a judge must be completely independent, free and freed from all forms of external influence and control, before he can perform his functions well. This is true of judges all over the

⁶⁶ Rivers State, Television Channel 22, available on <http://www.rstv22.tv/component/content/article/1-latest-news/278-fg-uncovers-corruption-in-judiciary.html> culled from Nigerian Tribune Newspaper pf 26th November, 2011 accessed on 21 May, 2012

⁶⁷ *ibid*;

⁶⁸ The Nigerian Voice, of 15th May, 2013, available at <http://www.thenigerianvoice.com/nvnews/113670/1/njc-probing-21-judges-for-corruption-cjn.html> accessed on 17th June, 2013

⁶⁹ available on <http://www.vanguardngr.com/2014/01/efcc-moves-prosecute-seven-corrupt-judges/> accessed on 10th January, 2014

⁷⁰ *ibid*;

world. But, it is perhaps true in Nigeria where naira is the lord and some people think that even justice is a commodity which can be bought and sold.”⁷¹

Unless judges play their respective key roles to the full in maintaining justice in Nigerian society impartially, there is a risk that a culture of impunity will prevail and justice can be for sale. Independence of judiciary connotes so many things. The judiciary must attain independence in all its ramifications. It must independently handle all matters pertaining to it. It must have independence as to administrative and financial matters. It must be independent as to its decision-making, appointments and promotions, training and education etc

The crises in Nigerian judiciary are prominent because of two things. For the importance of judiciary, the crises in it could be more devastating than crises in other arms of government. It is just like having ‘crises’ in the most important part of one’s body – heart. The crises in judiciary are prominent because ordinarily, as Nigerians’ ‘watchdog’ the judiciary is not supposed to be in crises. People talk about it because the judiciary supposed to intervene when other arms are in crises. Nigerians talk about it because other arms, with all due respect, have always been in crises of some sort. Logically and even constitutionally, Nigerians always expect other arms to be in crises and always expect the judiciary to determine the crises and declare who is right and who is wrong.⁷².

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⁷¹ P. Nnaemeka-Agu, “Enhancing the Efficacy and Independence of the Judiciary in the Third Republic” (1993) 14(3) *JUS* 9 at 16.

⁷² See section 6 of the 1999 Constitution